

**THE MEDIATING EFFECT OF METACOGNITIVE KNOWLEDGE ON THE
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN REFLECTIVE THINKING SKILLS IN
PROBLEM SOLVING AND MATHEMATICS ANXIETY
AMONG MATHEMATICS EDUCATION STUDENTS**

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 29

Issue 5

Pages: 656-673

Document ID: 2024PEMJ2783

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.14546157

Manuscript Accepted: 11-19-2024

The Mediating Effect of Metacognitive Knowledge on the Relationship Between Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem Solving and Mathematics Anxiety among Mathematics Education Students

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Abstract

The study aimed to determine the mediating effect of metacognitive knowledge on the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety among mathematics education students. The study was quantitative non-experimental research that utilized descriptive-correlational and mediation analyses. Using stratified random sampling, specifically proportional allocation for the sampling techniques and Slovin's formula with a 0.05 margin of error for the sample size, 96 randomly selected mathematics education students answered the surveys on the three variables. Mean, Pearson r , and Mediation Analysis using the Preacher and Hayes approach were used as statistical tools in the data analysis. Results showed that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and metacognitive knowledge is high. However, the level of mathematics anxiety is at a very low level. Results also revealed that the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety, between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and metacognitive knowledge, and between metacognitive knowledge and mathematics anxiety among mathematics education students have a significant relationship. The results revealed that metacognitive knowledge partially mediates the connection between reflective problem-solving skills and mathematics anxiety.

Keywords: *reflective thinking skills in problem-solving, metacognitive knowledge, mathematics anxiety, mediating effect, Philippines*

Introduction

Math anxiety can be described as a sense of stress, unease, and nervousness that hampers one's ability to perform mathematical tasks, including number manipulation and solving mathematical problems. This condition affects individuals in everyday life as well as academic scenarios (Ashcraft, 2002). It can manifest across all levels of education, ranging from primary school through university. It is a recognized issue both in K-12 education and tertiary education and, therefore, this subject has garnered significant attention as a research topic within the field of educational science (Jansen et al., 2013). As an example, in the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2012, conducted across 34 participating countries within the Organisation for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), 59% of 15-year-old students indicated frequent concerns about the difficulty of math classes, and 31% reported experiencing high levels of nervousness when working on math problems (OECD, 2013).

It is a pervasive issue that affects people of all ages across the globe. It is a concern that extends to all age groups. In the United States, for instance, approximately 93% of adults acknowledge experiencing some degree of math anxiety (Blazer, 2011). Estimates suggest that around 17% of the U.S. population grapples with significant levels of math anxiety (Ashcraft & Moore, 2009). In a group of adolescents in the United Kingdom, approximately 30% of participants are experiencing severe math anxiety, while an additional 18% also have similar experiences (Johnston-Wilder et al., 2018). According to some estimates, nearly 1 in 5 U.S. adults admit to experiencing severe math anxiety, and the vast majority express some level of unease regarding the subject. In a comprehensive survey of U.S. educators conducted by the EdWeek Research Center, math anxiety was a challenge for 67 percent of teachers' students, and 1 in 4 teachers admitted to feeling anxious when working with mathematics frequently (Sparks, 2020). According to Beilock (2019), roughly a quarter of students enrolled in four-year colleges are believed to encounter moderate to high levels of math anxiety. Additionally, a study has shown that counseling is necessary for 11% of university students in the US due to high levels of math anxiety.

In the Philippines, quantitative research revealed that 77% of Senior High School Students in the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Strand at Sorsogon State College-Sorsogon City Campus experienced math anxiety, specifically in pre-calculus. In another quantitative research, it was found that students had a notably high level of anxiety related to mathematics. A majority of them experienced significant math anxiety, especially when facing mathematics tests in a modular learning context. Moreover, these students were apprehensive about performing mathematical calculations and solving problems daily, indicating numerical anxiety, which disrupted their overall performance (Estonanto, 2017).

Examining this issue is crucial as the global community grapples with the prolonged impact of COVID-19. College students pursuing mathematics education need help with studying and acquiring knowledge due to limited face-to-face classes and blended learning approaches. Amid these significant challenges, the researcher investigates the existence of students' mathematics anxiety. The study also aimed to determine if students' proficiency in reflective thinking skills for problem-solving mitigates mathematics anxiety. This research significantly enhances the school's educational landscape by providing valuable insights. It offers a fresh perspective on the interplay between metacognitive knowledge, reflective thinking skills, and mathematics anxiety. The findings could contribute to improving strategies and understanding these dynamics. College administrators can use this study to develop program initiatives and

activities for effective and efficient mathematics teaching among mathematics education students.

Numerous studies have been done to identify reasons, establish conclusions, and find solutions to the seriousness of the situation. The researcher aims to analyze the importance of students' metacognitive knowledge as a mediating variable between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety. However, the researcher had not encountered a study in the Philippines, particularly in the locality, that covered all of the above characteristics. Studies have been conducted, such as those of Erdem and Arıkan (2023), entitled "The Relationship Between Reflective Thinking Skills in 8th-grade Middle School Students and Their Mathematics Anxiety." Rozgonjuk et al. (2020), entitled "Mathematics Anxiety among STEM and Social Sciences Students: The Roles of Mathematics Self-efficacy, and Deep and Surface Approach to Learning," focused on mathematics anxiety but not on the significant relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and metacognitive knowledge. The research participants were not mathematics education students and did not utilize mediation analysis as a statistical tool. Additionally, the relationship between metacognitive knowledge and math anxiety has not been explored so far. Based on this premise, the researcher felt it necessary to conduct this research to determine the mediating role of metacognitive knowledge on the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety of mathematics education students. Further, the study could also indicate whether metacognitive knowledge applies to reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety among students in the academic track. Also, this research highlights the significant impact that metacognitive knowledge may have on enhancing reflective thinking skills and reducing mathematics anxiety. The study's primary aim is to explore how metacognitive knowledge influences the link between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and math anxiety among mathematics education students. It seeks to illuminate the strategies for enhancing classroom practices and lesson planning. Specifically, the research will provide a detailed perspective on the correlations between the measured variables, identifying factors that may reduce math anxiety. The collected data will be used to create and refine strategies to mitigate and prevent mathematics anxiety.

Finally, this study will enrich the existing literature in the institution and broader educational forums. The manuscript and its findings will be distributed within the institution and potentially presented at research conferences. This dissemination will promote scholarly exchange and facilitate the application of the research findings. As a result, the study's significance and outcomes will reach a wider audience, enabling them to address the identified issues and implement the proposed recommendations.

Research Questions

This study aimed to determine the mediating role of metacognitive knowledge on the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety of mathematics education students. Specifically, this attempted to achieve the following objectives:

1. To determine the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving in terms of:
 - 1.1. questioning;
 - 1.2. evaluation; and
 - 1.3. causation.
2. To determine the level of Metacognitive Knowledge in terms of:
 - 2.1. declarative knowledge;
 - 2.2. procedural knowledge; and
 - 2.3. conditional knowledge
3. To determine the level of Mathematics Anxiety in terms of:
 - 3.1. appraisal towards external stimulus;
 - 3.2. face expression;
 - 3.3. arousal; and
 - 3.4. action tendencies
4. To determine the significant relationship between:
 - 4.1. appraisal towards external stimulus;
 - 4.2. face expression;
 - 4.3. arousal; and
 - 4.4. action tendencies
5. To determine the mediating effect of Metacognitive knowledge on the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety.

Methodology

Research Design

The research design employed in this study was a quantitative, non-experimental approach that involved using a descriptive-correlational technique and conducting mediation analysis. The study investigated mediating variables, which are behavioral, biological, psychological, or social constructs that transmit the influence of one variable to another, to comprehend the mechanisms through which one variable affects another. In this context, non-experimental research refers to studies that do not involve manipulating

an independent variable, randomly assigning individuals to conditions, or ordering of conditions. It is important to note that simply categorizing these methods based on what they are not maybe unfair (Price et al., 2014).

This study employed non-experimental methods to explore the relationship between reflective skills in problem-solving, metacognitive knowledge, and mathematics anxiety among mathematics education students. The insights gained from this research can reveal how metacognitive knowledge and reflective thinking influence math anxiety, thereby informing the development of educational strategies and curricula in teacher education programs.

Furthermore, descriptive studies were crucial in the research design as they provided tools to summarize, analyze, and comprehend data. They offered insights into central tendencies, variability, and distribution of data. Measures like mean, median, and mode provided average values, while range, variance, and standard deviation revealed data dispersion. Tools like histograms, box plots, and frequency tables visualized data distribution. They aided in data-driven decisions, identifying trends, and communicating findings effectively (Price et al., 2014).

This study used descriptive statistics to efficiently summarize and analyze collected data, providing insights into the central tendencies, variability, and distribution of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving, metacognitive knowledge, and mathematics anxiety within the participant group. These statistics served as a foundation for understanding complex dynamics and identifying patterns, contributing to meaningful conclusions in the study.

Then on the other hand, correlational research was defined as a type of non-experimental investigation where the researcher examined two variables and assessed their statistical relationship without trying to control external factors. There were two primary reasons why researchers interested in statistical correlations between variables might opt for a correlational study instead of an experiment (Price et al., 2014).

In this context, correlational research proves valuable in examining statistical relationships between variables like reflective thinking skills in problem-solving, metacognitive knowledge, and mathematics anxiety without manipulating them in a controlled environment. This approach acknowledges the complexity of real-world educational settings, providing insights crucial for tailoring effective teaching strategies to support student's success in mathematics within the constraints of a non-experimental approach.

Mediation analysis, in its simplest form, represented the addition of a third variable to the $X \rightarrow Y$ relation, whereby X caused the mediator, M , and caused Y , so $X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$. This analytical approach provided a deeper understanding of the mechanisms through which the independent variable affected the dependent variable. By identifying and exploring the role of the mediator, researchers gained insights into the underlying processes and pathways that contributed to the observed relationship between X and Y . Mediation analysis was particularly valuable in uncovering the intervening variables that explained how and why X changes led to Y changes.

In this context, the researcher explored the intricate connections between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving (X), metacognitive knowledge (M), and mathematics anxiety (Y). The analysis revealed a relationship ($X \rightarrow M \rightarrow Y$), illustrating how metacognitive knowledge mediates the influence of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving on mathematics anxiety. These insights are crucial for customizing teaching strategies and curricula to optimize mathematical learning in our educational context.

The independent variable in this study was reflective thinking skills in problem-solving, while the dependent variable was mathematics anxiety, and the mediating variable was metacognitive knowledge. In this study, the researcher determined the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety and the mediating effect of metacognitive knowledge on the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety among mathematics education students.

Respondents

The participants in this research comprise students studying mathematics education at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology in the Municipality of Kapalong, Davao del Norte. Specifically, these students are enrolled in the BSED- Mathematics program across all academic years.

Further, Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents of this study. Hence, to ensure a fair and accurate sample, the researcher used stratified random sampling with proportional allocation, guided by Slovin's formula and a margin of error of 0.05. The population is segmented into subgroups known as "strata" in stratified random sampling, and participants are chosen using random sampling within each stratum. The overall sample is formed by combining the samples from all the strata (Nguyen et al., 2020). In this study, the strata represent the four programs within the education department at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology (KCAST).

The total number of participants in the study was drawn from five sections of mathematics education students, totaling 245 individuals. Sample sizes were determined as follows: 74 students from a total of 119 in BSED-Mathematics 1st Year, 31 from 50 in BSED-Mathematics 2nd Year, 27 from 43 in BSED-Mathematics 3rd Year, and 20 from 33 in BSED-Mathematics 4th Year. In total, 152 students were selected from the 245 mathematics education students' pool.

The criteria for selecting participants included enrollment in the first semester of the 2023-2024 academic year in the BSED-Mathematics program at Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology, along with a demonstrated history of active engagement in learning mathematics during their junior and senior high school years.

Table 1. *Distribution of Respondents*

<i>Year Level</i>	<i>Population</i>	<i>Sample</i>	<i>Percentage</i>
1st Year	119	74	30.13%
2nd Year	50	31	12.66%
3rd Year	43	27	10.89%
4th Year	33	20	8.36%
Total	245	152	62.04%

Instrument

The Likert scale, widely used in research, assesses individuals' opinions on a topic through statements or questions, offering response options from "strongly agree" to "strongly disagree," across various levels of intensity. It's commonly applied by social science researchers in behavioral, educational, and health contexts (Spector, 1992).

In this study, a Likert scale was employed to evaluate respondents' reactions to statements concerning various dimensions. Through the Likert scale, respondents' levels of agreement or disagreement with each statement were measured to assess academic commitment, behavioral engagement, and instructional support. With validation from experts, the researcher analyzed the data to explore how behavioral engagement influences the link between academic dedication and instructional support.

The study utilized three Likert scales outsourced from the web to measure variables. The instrument for reflective thinking skills toward problem-solving was from Can's (2015) study, showing a Cronbach alpha of 0.83, indicating good internal consistency. The instrument for mathematics anxiety was from Rameli's (2016) study, with a Cronbach Alpha of 0.91, showing very high internal consistency. The instrument for metacognitive knowledge was from Sariçoban and Kirmizi's (2020) study, with a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.833, indicating good internal consistency.

Moreover, the survey research questionnaires were validated to ensure content validity. The initial draft of the research instruments was shared with the research committee for feedback and recommendations on enhancing clarity and presentation, with subsequent revisions made accordingly. The final version was then reviewed by the research panel for further examination and refinement, incorporating any errors, critiques, and suggestions provided by expert validators. The culmination of the validators' evaluations determined the questionnaire's final status.

Procedure

In gathering data, the researchers observed the following steps.

Seeking the Permission to Conduct the Study. The researcher sought permission from the College President of KCAST through a letter allowing the researcher to conduct a study among mathematics education students. After getting the approval of the College President, the researcher sent letters to the College Registrar and the Vice-President for Academic Affairs. Then, the program coordinator for the Bachelor of Secondary Education—Mathematics was informed by the researcher and the panel members to ensure their full awareness of the study's implementation.

Distribution and Retrieval of the Questionnaire. With the college president's approval, the researcher asked for help from the program coordinator of the Bachelor of Secondary Education major in Mathematics and their class mayors to distribute the questionnaire through face-to-face interaction.

Collection and Tabulation of the Data. At this point, the research tool is retrieved, inspected, and gathered to compile the collected data. The researcher found it convenient since 152 students were recognized as mathematics education students.

Data Analysis

The following statistical tools were employed:

Mean. This statistical tool was used to determine the respondents' average level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving, mathematics anxiety, and metacognitive knowledge.

Pearson r. This statistical tool was utilized to assess the relationships between Reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety, Reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and metacognitive knowledge, and Metacognitive knowledge and mathematics anxiety among the respondents.

Mediation Analysis using Preacher and Hayes Approach. This statistical tool addressed the main research question concerning whether metacognitive knowledge mediates the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety among the respondents.

Ethical Considerations

The study involved mathematics education students from Kapalong College of Agriculture, Sciences, and Technology. The researcher prioritized the participants' safety, rights, and trust, ensuring that their well-being and the purpose of the study were treated with utmost

care and fairness.

Maintaining high ethical standards is imperative when conducting research involving human participants. The primary goal of this quantitative investigation was to ensure the ethical integrity of the study, with a focus on safeguarding the welfare of the human participants. The researcher carefully considered and adhered to the ethical principles outlined by Denzin and Lincoln (2011), which revolve around three core principles: informed consent, risk of harm, anonymity, and confidentiality, as well as conflict of interest.

The first core principle of ethical considerations is informed consent. This involves thoroughly disclosing the study's requirements, how the data will be used, and any potential consequences to the participants. Participants are required to give their explicit, active, and written consent to participate in the study. They must also acknowledge their awareness of their right to access their information and the option to withdraw their consent at any time. Establishing an agreement between the researcher and the participants is a key step in obtaining informed consent (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

The second core principle encompasses risk of harm, maintaining confidentiality, and anonymity. It focuses on safeguarding participants so that even the researcher cannot link individuals to the data they provide. It also involves preventing the disclosure of participants' identities to anyone other than authorized individuals (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

The researcher placed great importance on ensuring the safety and preserving the anonymity and personal information of the participants, considering them as valuable contributors to the research. The researcher took measures to remove any identifying information from the data to maintain a completely confidential data collection process. Clean data collection means no information can be used to identify the respondents, such as names or addresses (any identifying information that may exist would be stored separately in protected files).

The third core aspect of ethical considerations involves conflicts of interest. This entails acknowledging any pre-existing relationships or previous activities the researcher might have that could lead to a conflict of interest. Such conflicts must be transparently disclosed in an ethics approval application, allowing the ethics committee to guide how to address the conflict. Conflicts of interest can occur when an individual prioritizes their interests or commitments over their responsibilities as a researcher or is perceived to do so. These conflicts can be real, hypothetical, or perceived and may involve financial incentives or non-monetary rewards. Conflicts of interest can compromise a researcher's objectivity and judgment, or they may be perceived as affecting these qualities, which can undermine the reliability of the research findings (Denzin & Lincoln, 2011).

It is important to note that this study had no external factors related to the researcher that could influence the outcomes, as the respondents were also students, eliminating any conflict of interest. Conflict of interest usually occurs when researchers can coerce participation through threats or penalties, such as teachers threatening to fail students or principals threatening to terminate teachers for non-compliance.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the findings and results on the mediating effect of metacognitive knowledge on the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety. Analyses and interpretations of data were done parallel to the research objectives.

Level of Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving in Terms of Questioning

The level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator questioning. The responses of first to fourth-year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 2 is the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving as perceived by students in terms of questioning. The data revealed that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving in terms of questioning had a mean of 3.72, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving in terms of questioning is oftentimes observed.

Table 2. *Level of Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving in Terms of Questioning*

<i>Questioning</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Asking questions to myself to understand why I cannot solve the problem	3.99	High
2. Trying to find a better way of solving by questioning the paths followed by my peers to solve the problem	4.03	High
3. Asking questions to myself to find different ways of solving the problem	3.99	High
4. Thinking about which information I need for solution	4.10	High
5. Asking questions to myself to determine what is given and required class	4.11	High
Overall	3.72	High

The highest mean is 4.11, which is a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 5 – asking questions to myself to determine what is given and required in class.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.76 but with a descriptive equivalent of high.

This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 1 – asking questions to myself to understand why I cannot solve the problem, and item no. 3 – asking questions to myself to find different ways of solving the problem.

Level of Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving in Terms of Evaluation

The level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator evaluation. The responses of first- to fourth-year mathematics major students to each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 3 is the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving as perceived by students in terms of evaluation. The data revealed that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving in terms of evaluation had a total mean of 4.00 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving in terms of evaluation is oftentimes observed.

The highest mean is 4.07, which is a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 5 – comparing my solution with the solutions of my peers and evaluate my solution.

Table 3. *Level of Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving in Terms of Evaluation*

<i>Evaluation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Thinking about a better solution after solving a problem	3.98	High
2. Evaluating the possible solutions one by one to find a better solution to the next problem	3.95	High
3. Going over and evaluate the operations I have performed after solving a problem	3.95	High
4. Checking the operations I have performed after solving a problem and finding the result	4.05	High
5. Comparing my solution with the solutions of my peers and evaluate my solution	4.07	High
Overall	4.00	High

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.95 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 2 – evaluating the possible solutions one by one to find a better solution to the next problem, and from item no. 3 – Going over and evaluate the operations I have performed after solving a problem.

Level of Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving in Terms of Causation

The level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator causation. The responses of first to fourth-year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 4 is the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving as perceived by students in terms of causation. The data revealed that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving in terms of causation had a mean of 3.94, with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicated that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving in terms of causation is oftentimes observed.

Table 4. *Level of Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving in Terms of Causation*

<i>Causation</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Carefully thinking about why I perform which operation while solving a problem	3.93	High
2. Thinking about the reasons for the operations and try to establish a connection with the result I have found	3.97	High
3. Thinking about the problem I have previously solved and create connections between them based on similarities and differences	3.93	High
4. Performing each operation by thinking previous and next stages	3.91	High
5. Considering the potential causes and root factors contributing to the issue at hand	3.92	High
Overall	3.94	High

The highest mean is 3.97, which is a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 2 – thinking about the reasons for the operations and try to establish a connection with the result I have found.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.91 but with a descriptive equivalent of high.

This means that the item is oftentimes observed by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 4 – performing each operation by thinking previous and next stages.

Summary of the Level of Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving

Presented in Table 5 is the overall level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving in terms of questioning, evaluation, and causation. The data revealed that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving as perceived by mathematics education students has a total mean of 3.89 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving as perceived by students is oftentimes observed.

Further, the highest mean is 4.00 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that the level of reflective thinking skills

in problem-solving as perceived by students in terms of evaluation is oftentimes observed.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is clear instruction, which obtained a mean of 3.72 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving in terms of questioning is oftentimes observed.

Lastly, causation obtained a mean of 3.94 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving in terms of causation is oftentimes observed.

Table 5. Summary on the Level of Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving

<i>Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Questioning	3.72	High
Evaluation	4.00	High
Causation	3.94	High
Overall	3.89	High

Level of Metacognitive Knowledge of Students in Terms of Declarative Knowledge

The level of metacognitive knowledge was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, declarative knowledge. The responses of first- to fourth-year mathematics major students to each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 6 is the level of metacognitive knowledge of first to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of declarative knowledge. The data revealed that the level of metacognitive knowledge in declarative knowledge has a total mean of 4.01 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive knowledge of first to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of declarative knowledge is oftentimes manifested.

The highest mean is 4.10 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the involved respondents oftentimes manifest the item. This is from item no. 1 – understanding my strength and weaknesses.

Table 6. Level of Metacognitive Knowledge of Students in Terms of Declarative Knowledge

<i>Declarative Knowledge</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Understanding my strength and weaknesses	4.10	High
2. Identifying the kind of information that is important to learn	4.09	High
3. Organizing relevant information	4.04	High
4. Knowing the expectation of instructor in learning	3.93	High
5. Remembering important information	3.89	High
Overall	4.01	Very High

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.89 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study.

This is from item no. 5 – remembering important information.

Level of Metacognitive Knowledge of Students in Terms of Procedural Knowledge

The level of metacognitive knowledge was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator of procedural knowledge. The responses of first- to fourth-year mathematics major students to each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 7 is the level of metacognitive knowledge of first to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of procedural knowledge. The data revealed that the level of metacognitive knowledge in terms of procedural knowledge has a total mean of 4.00 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive knowledge of first to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of procedural knowledge is oftentimes manifested.

Table 7. Level of Metacognitive Knowledge of Students in Terms of Procedural Knowledge

<i>Procedural Knowledge</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Using strategies that have worked in the past	4.03	High
2. Having specific purpose for each strategy use	3.91	High
3. Being aware of strategies to use	3.89	High
4. Using helpful learning strategies	4.18	High
5. Applying specific strategies or procedures when faced with complex problem-solving tasks	4.01	High
Overall	4.00	High

The highest mean is 4.18 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 4 – using helpful learning strategies

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.89 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents of the study.

This is from item no. 3 – being aware of strategies to use.

Level of Metacognitive Knowledge of Students in Terms of Conditional Knowledge

The level of metacognitive knowledge was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator conditional knowledge. The responses of first- to fourth-year mathematics major students to each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 8 is the level of metacognitive knowledge of first to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of conditional knowledge. The data revealed that the level of metacognitive knowledge in terms of conditional knowledge has a total mean of 4.04 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive knowledge of first to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of conditional knowledge is oftentimes manifested.

Table 8. Level of Metacognitive Knowledge of Students in Terms of Conditional Knowledge

<i>Conditional Knowledge</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Learning best when familiar with topic	4.18	High
2. Utilizing different learning strategies depending on the situation	3.95	High
3. Motivating self to learn when needed	4.14	High
4. Using intellectual strengths to compensate for weaknesses	3.91	High
5. Knowing when each strategy to use will be the most effective	4.03	High
Overall	4.04	High

The highest mean is 4.18 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the involved respondents. This is from item no. 1 – learning best when familiar with topic.

In contrast, the lowest mean is 3.91 but with a descriptive equivalent of high. This means that the item is oftentimes manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 4 – using intellectual strengths to compensate for weaknesses.

Summary on the Level of Metacognitive Knowledge

Presented in Table 9 is the overall level of metacognitive knowledge in terms of declarative knowledge, procedural knowledge, and conditional knowledge. The data revealed that the level of metacognitive knowledge of first to fourth-year mathematics education students has a total mean of 4.02 with the descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive knowledge of mathematics education students is oftentimes manifested.

Further, the highest mean is 4.04 with the descriptive equivalent of very high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive knowledge in terms of conditional knowledge is always manifested.

Table 9. Summary on the Level of Metacognitive Knowledge

<i>Metacognitive Knowledge</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
Declarative Knowledge	4.01	High
Procedural Knowledge	4.00	High
Conditional Knowledge	4.04	High
Overall	4.02	High

In contrast, the lowest indicators are skill satisfaction and academic satisfaction which obtained a mean of 4.00 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive knowledge in terms of procedural knowledge is oftentimes manifested.

Lastly, declarative knowledge obtained a mean of 4.01 with a descriptive equivalent of high. This indicates that the level of metacognitive knowledge in terms of declarative knowledge is always manifested.

Level of Math Anxiety in Terms of Appraisal Towards External Stimulus

The level of math anxiety was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator appraisal towards external stimulus. The responses of first to fourth-year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Table 10. Level of Math Anxiety in Terms of Appraisal Towards External Stimulus

<i>Appraisal Towards External Stimulus</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Feeling worry when I learn math concept that involve many symbols	1.60	Very Low
2. Feeling worry when I think of the good examination result as the criteria in the selection process to the higher education level	1.73	Very Low
3. Feeling worry with math teachers who likes to ask questions to the students	1.69	Very Low
4. Feeling anxious once I see the examination question asked is different with what regularly asked	1.65	Very Low
5. Feeling worry in learning this subject because of my previous moderate math achievement	1.70	Very Low
Overall	1.68	Very Low

Presented in Table 10 is the level of math anxiety of first- to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of appraisal of external stimuli. The data revealed that the level of math anxiety in terms of appraisal towards external stimulus has a total mean of

1.68, with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This indicates that the level of math anxiety of first- to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of appraisal towards external stimuli is never manifested.

The highest mean is 1.73, with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This means that the respondents never manifest the item. This is from item no. 2 – feeling worry when I think of the good examination result as the criteria in the selection process to the higher education level.

In contrast, the lowest 1.60 with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This means that the item is never manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 1 – feeling worry when I learn math concept that involve many symbols.

Level of Math Anxiety in Terms of Arousal

The level of math anxiety was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator arousal. The responses of first- to fourth-year mathematics major students to each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 11 is the level of math anxiety of first to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of arousal. The data revealed that the level of math anxiety in terms of arousal has a total mean of 1.65, with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This indicates that the level of math anxiety of first to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of arousal is never manifested.

The highest mean is 1.71, with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This means that the involved respondents never manifest the item. This is from item no. 3– daydreaming if I could not answer math examination questions.

Table 11. *Level of Math Anxiety in Terms of Arousal*

<i>Arousal</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Feeling hurt in my head when answering tough math questions	1.61	Very Low
2. Feeling my heart beating fast when teacher asks me how good am I in certain math topic	1.64	Very Low
3. Daydreaming if I could not answer math examination questions	1.71	Very Low
4. Feeling my palm sweating when answering math examination questions	1.65	Very Low
5. Feeling my hands trembling before answering math examination questions	1.61	Very Low
Overall	1.65	Very Low

In contrast, the lowest mean is 1.61 with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This means that the item is never manifested by the respondents. This is from item no. 1 – feeling hurt in my head when answering tough math questions and item no. 5 – feeling my hands trembling before answering math examination questions.

Level of Math Anxiety in Terms of Face Expression

The level of math anxiety was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator, face expression. The responses of first to fourth-year mathematics major students on each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 12 is the level of math anxiety of first- to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of facial expression. The data revealed that the level of math anxiety in terms of facial expression has a total mean of 1.68, with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This indicates that the level of math anxiety of first- to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of facial expressions is never manifested.

The highest mean is 1.70, with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This means that the respondents never manifest the item. This is from item no. 1 – frowning my forehead when I could not answer math question asked by teacher, item no. 3 – feeling my face is easily sweating before math examination begin, and item no. 5 – experiencing visible signs of discomfort, such as facial expressions like tension, when working on math-related tasks or during math assessments

Table 12. *Level of Math Anxiety in Terms of Face Expression*

<i>Face Expression</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Description</i>
1. Frowning my forehead when I could not answer math question asked by teacher	1.70	Very Low
2. Feeling my face hot when sitting for math examination	1.62	Very Low
3. Feeling my face is easily sweating before math examination begin	1.70	Very Low
4. Snapping-lip because I worry that I could not understand the math topic teach by teacher	1.67	Very Low
5. Experiencing visible signs of discomfort, such as facial expressions like tension, when working on math-related tasks or during math assessments	1.70	Very Low
Overall	1.68	Very Low

In contrast, the lowest mean is 1.62 but with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This means that the item is never manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 2 – feeling my face hot when sitting for math examination.

Level of Math Anxiety in Terms of Action Tendencies

The level of math anxiety was measured through the survey questionnaire with the indicator action tendencies. The responses of first-

to fourth-year mathematics major students to each indicator were presented and analyzed below.

Presented in Table 13 is the level of math anxiety of first to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of action tendencies. The data revealed that the level of math anxiety in terms of action tendencies has a total mean of 1.68, with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This indicates that the level of math anxiety of first to fourth-year mathematics education students in terms of action tendencies is never manifested.

The highest mean is 1.74, with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This means that the respondents never manifest the item. This is from item no. 1 – keeping silent during mathematics class because I scared to be asked math question and item no. 2 – playing with pen (others objects) when I could not answer math question during the examination.

Table 13. *Level of Math Anxiety in Terms of Action Tendencies*

Action Tendencies	Mean	Description
1. Keeping silent during mathematics class because I scared to be asked math question	1.74	Very Low
2. Playing with pen (others objects) when I could not answer math question during the examination	1.74	Very Low
3. Looking at my friends when I could not answer math questions given by the teacher	1.70	Very Low
4. Going to the toilet during math class to avoid from being ask a question	1.53	Very Low
5. Trying to complete the math examination faster before other students done	1.69	Very Low
Overall	1.68	Very Low

In contrast, the lowest mean is 1.53 but with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This means that the item is never manifested by the respondents of the study. This is from item no. 4 – going to the toilet during math class to avoid from being ask a question.

Summary of the Level of Math Anxiety

Presented in Table 14 is the overall level of math anxiety in terms of appraisal towards external stimulus, arousal, facial expression, and action tendencies. The data revealed that the level of math anxiety of first to fourth-year mathematics education students has a total mean of 1.67 with the descriptive equivalent of very low. This indicates that the level of math anxiety of first to fourth-year mathematics students is never manifested.

Table 14. *Summary on the Level of Math Anxiety*

Math Anxiety	Mean	Description
Appraisal towards external stimulus	1.68	Very Low
Arousal	1.68	Very Low
Face Expression	1.65	Very Low
Action Tendencies	1.68	Very Low
Overall	1.67	Very Low

Further, the highest mean is 1.68, with the descriptive equivalent being very low. This indicates that the level of math anxiety in terms of appraisal towards external stimulus, arousal, and action tendencies is never manifested.

In contrast, the lowest indicator is facial expression, which obtained a mean of 1.65 with a descriptive equivalent of very low. This indicates that the level of math anxiety in terms of facial expression is never manifested.

Significant Relationship between Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving and Math Anxiety

Presented in Table 15 is the result of the significant relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and math anxiety, $r(152) = -0.739$, $p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a negative and significant relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and math anxiety. Additionally, it implies that mathematics anxiety decreases as reflective thinking skills increase.

Table 15. *Significant Relationship between Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving and Math Anxiety*

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @ = 0.05
Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving	3.99			
Math Anxiety	1.67	-.739	<.001	Ho Rejected

Significant Relationship between Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving and Metacognitive Knowledge

Presented in Table 16 is the result of the significant relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and metacognitive knowledge, $r(150) = .911$, $p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This means a positive and significant relationship exists between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and metacognitive knowledge. This implies that metacognitive knowledge increases as reflective thinking skills in problem-solving increase.

Table 16. Significant Relationship between Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving and Metacognitive Knowledge

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving	3.99			
Metacognitive Knowledge	4.02	.911	<.001	Ho Rejected

Significant Relationship between Metacognitive Knowledge and Math Anxiety

Presented in Table 17 is the result of the significant relationship between metacognitive knowledge and math anxiety, $r(150) = -0.746$, $p < .001$. Since the probability value ($p < .001$) is less than the level of significance ($\alpha = 0.05$), the null hypothesis is rejected. This means that there is a negative and significant relationship between metacognitive knowledge and math anxiety. This implies that as metacognitive knowledge increases, mathematics anxiety decreases.

Table 17. Significant Relationship between Metacognitive Knowledge and Math Anxiety

Variable	Mean	R-Value	P-Value	Decision @=0.05
Metacognitive Knowledge	4.02			
Math Anxiety	1.67	-0.746	<.001	Ho Rejected

The Mediating Effect of Metacognitive Knowledge on the relationship between Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving and Mathematics Anxiety among Mathematics Education Students

Preacher and Hayes's mediation analysis approach was utilized in this study to determine the mediating effect of metacognitive knowledge on the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety among mathematics education students. It is a regression-based bootstrap approach similar to SEM (Structural Equation Modeling) used for analyzing mediation. It consists of two steps that reflect the recommendation for mediation analysis. In step 1, the direct and indirect effects are tested for significance. Step 2 involves defining the type of effect and mediation, which is classified into partial and full mediation.

Full mediation is achieved if the direct effect is not significant and the indirect effect is significant. This means that only the indirect effect of the mediator exists. On the other hand, partial mediation happens when the direct effect is significant.

Mediation Analysis

Table 18 shows the direct effect of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving towards math anxiety. Based on the result, the direct effect of reflective thinking skills in (IV) on math anxiety (DV) is significant [$\beta = -0.253$, $SE = 0.092$, 95% CI (-0.433, -0.072)]. Since the confidence interval in the direct effect does not include zero, it indicates that the direct effect of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving is significant ($\beta = -0.253$, $p < .001$).

Table 18. Direct Effects

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving → Math Anxiety	-0.253	0.092	-2.747	.006	-0.433	-0.072

Additionally, it also means that every unit increased in reflective thinking skills in problem-solving (IV) will entice a 0.253 decrease in mathematics anxiety (DV).

Table 19 shows the indirect effect of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving (IV) on metacognitive knowledge (MV) and math anxiety (DV) showed [$\beta = -0.278$, $SE = 0.084$, 95% CI (-0.444, -0.113)], and it indicates that the confidence interval does not include zero. At 0.05 significance level, the null hypothesis is rejected, $p < .001$. This announces that the mediating variable, which is metacognitive knowledge, mediates the relationship between the independent variable, reflective thinking skills in problem-solving, and the dependent variable, which is math anxiety.

Table 19. Indirect Effects

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving → Metacognitive Knowledge → Math Anxiety	-0.278	0.084	3.296	<.001	-0.444	-0.113

Furthermore, it can be perceived that every unit increased in the reflective thinking skills in problem-solving (IV) will entice a 0.278 decrease in mathematics anxiety (DV) as it goes through the metacognitive knowledge (MV).

Moreover, Table 20 shows that reflective thinking skills in problem-solving significantly influence math anxiety among mathematics education students. It means that even without the presence of the mediating variable, metacognitive knowledge and reflective thinking

skills in problem-solving already affect math anxiety among mathematics education students. Since the effect is significant, it can be concluded that the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety is only partly mediated by metacognitive knowledge.

Also, as shown in the results, it could be inferred that an increase in the reflective thinking skills in problem-solving (IV) will entice a 0.531 decrease in mathematics anxiety (DV) in every unit. The result stipulates that reflective thinking skills in problem-solving (IV) are significantly affecting mathematics anxiety (DV).

Table 20. Total Effects

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving → Math Anxiety	-0.531	.039	-13.524	<.001	-0.608	-0.454

Additionally, Table 21 below provides further information as to why the mediating effect of metacognitive knowledge is partial to the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety. It can be observed in the table that the effect of metacognitive knowledge (MV) on mathematics anxiety (DV) is significant ($p < .001$). Further, their confidence interval shows negative lower and upper intervals, and for an interval that ranges from negative values, we know the interval does not contain zero (or the null value), then suggests that there is a significant effect because the null hypothesis is accepted when the confidence interval includes zero.

Table 21. Path Coefficients

	Estimate	Std. Error	z-value	p	95% Confidence Interval	
					Lower	Upper
Metacognitive Knowledge → Math Anxiety	-0.308	0.093	-3.320	<.001	-0.490	-0.126
Reflective Thinking Skills → Math Anxiety	-0.253	0.092	-2.747	.006	-0.433	-0.072
Reflective Thinking Skills → Metacognitive Knowledge	0.903	0.033	27.257	<.001	0.838	0.968

On the other hand, the table shows that there is still a significant effect of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving (IV) to mathematics anxiety (DV) ($p < .001$). This means that even without the inclusion of metacognitive knowledge (MV), the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving (IV) and mathematics anxiety (DV) is still significant. Additionally, this indicates that metacognitive knowledge (MV) only partially mediates the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving (IV) and mathematics anxiety (DV) and that other possible mediating variables are not mentioned in this study. Similarly, there is a significant effect of metacognitive knowledge (MV) on mathematics anxiety (DV) ($p < .001$).

In addition to the result of the study, Figure 3 shows the path estimates between Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving and Mathematics Anxiety (Path C), Reflective Thinking Skills in Problem-Solving and Metacognitive Knowledge (Path A), and Metacognitive Knowledge and Mathematics Anxiety (Path B). It revealed that reflective thinking skills in problem-solving significantly influenced mathematics anxiety, $\beta = -0.253$, $p < .001$. Also, reflective thinking skills in problem-solving significantly affected metacognitive knowledge, $\beta = 0.9$, $p < .001$. Lastly, metacognitive knowledge is a significant predictor of mathematics anxiety, $\beta = -0.308$, $p < .001$.

Conclusions

This section consists of the overall summary of the study, particularly the results and their implications. Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn in answer to the objectives:

The level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving as perceived by the mathematics education students who demonstrated reflective thinking skills in problem-solving is high. Thus, it fosters a positive foundation for effective mathematical problem-solving and highlights the importance of nurturing and enhancing these skills within educational programs to empower students to approach mathematical challenges thoughtfully.

On the other hand, the level of metacognitive knowledge among mathematics education students who demonstrated metacognitive knowledge is high. Thus, they cultivate a heightened awareness and understanding of their cognitive processes.

Moreover, the level of mathematics anxiety among mathematics education students who demonstrated mathematics anxiety is very low. Thus, it implies that mathematics students are in a potentially positive and conducive learning environment regarding mathematical tasks.

Based on the findings, there is a significant relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety, as it is affirmed that mathematics anxiety in a general context is more likely to be affected by reflective thinking skills in problem-solving. Therefore, as perceived by students, reflective thinking skills in problem-solving immensely influence their mathematics

anxieties, which stipulates a significant relationship between the two variables.

Based on the study's findings, a negative and significant relationship exists between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and metacognitive knowledge. Therefore, students' metacognitive knowledge and reflective thinking skills in problem-solving, as perceived by students, are mutually reinforcing throughout their mathematics learning process. Hence, as students perceive, reflective thinking is immensely influenced by their metacognitive knowledge, which stipulates a significant relationship between the two variables.

Also, there is a negative and significant relationship between metacognitive knowledge and mathematics anxiety. Therefore, tailoring metacognitive knowledge to students' math learning enhances the overall attitude toward mathematics-related activities. Thus, students' metacognitive knowledge immensely influences their mathematics anxieties, stipulating a significant relationship between the two variables.

Furthermore, the mediation analysis revealed that metacognitive knowledge has partially mediated the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety. Therefore, the inclusion of metacognitive knowledge can affect the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety. However, from the context of the results, these stipulate that the indirect pathway partially mediates the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety through metacognitive knowledge, a claim supported by the estimation of a significant indirect effect.

The result also confirms the Theory of Cognitive Appraisal, which was developed by Lazarus (1984), which states that cognitive appraisal allows individuals to evaluate a stimulus and form a response to it. There are two component processes of cognitive appraisal: primary and secondary appraisal. Primary appraisal involves evaluating the significance of the stimulus, while secondary appraisal involves evaluating one's ability to cope with the stimulus.

The suggestions of the researcher are established based on the results and the wholeness of the paper. In light of the findings as mentioned above of the study, the following recommendations were made:

The level of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving as perceived by mathematics education students is high. However, among the items of each indicator of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving, it was found that questioning had the lowest mean result. Therefore, these students may proactively request their teachers to implement teaching strategies to foster questioning, provide guidance on formulating meaningful inquiries, and incorporate diverse problem scenarios. These measures aim to enhance the depth and quality of questioning, contributing to a more comprehensive development of reflective thinking skills in problem-solving.

Moreover, the level of metacognitive knowledge among mathematics education students is high. However, among the items of each indicator of metacognitive knowledge, it was found that procedural knowledge was the item with the lowest mean result. It is, therefore, suggested that these students focus on strengthening procedural knowledge by actively engaging in practice opportunities and collaborative learning. Emphasizing the systematic application of strategies in problem-solving scenarios and peer interaction can enhance their proficiency in procedural knowledge within the broader scope of metacognitive skills.

Furthermore, the level of mathematics anxiety in mathematics education students are very low. However, among the items of each indicator of mathematics anxiety, it was found that face expression was the item with the lowest mean result. It is therefore suggested that these students may benefit from engaging in emotion regulation strategies and exploring relaxation techniques to manage any subtle expressions of anxiety during mathematical tasks. Encouraging open communication about challenges and seeking support can also contribute to a more positive experience in mathematics education.

Finally, as metacognitive knowledge partially mediates the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety, it is recommended that future researchers investigate other variables that could fully mediate the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety. They are encouraged to utilize other methodologies, factors, or variables the study could not cover. Also, they might conduct it in different locales and/or with larger-scale participants. Since the participants for this research were mathematics students, it is also recommended that they study the mediating effect of metacognitive knowledge on the relationship between reflective thinking skills in problem-solving and mathematics anxiety among non-mathematics students.

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